

IDENTIFICATION OF POTENTIAL CAUSES OF CLOGGING AND DEVELOPMENT OF A MACHINE LEARNING-BASED PREDICTION MODEL

Habiba HOUARI¹, Samir HAMASSI², Souaad TAHRAOUI³, Imène AMEUR⁴ And Chaimaâ KHELOUFI⁵

¹ Laboratoire de Productique de Tlemcen (MELT) ,Ecole national polytechnique d'Oran,
habiba.houari@enp-oran.dz

² ECAM-EPMI : 13 boulevard de l'Hautil - 95092 CERGY-PONTOISE CEDEX
s.hamaci@ecam-epmi.com

³ Electronic Departement, Hassiba Benbouali University, Chlef Algeria, Signals, Systems and Artificial Intelligence Laboratory 2SAIL Chlef Algeria.
s.tahraoui@univ-chlef.dz

⁴Ecole national polytechnique d'Oran
imene.am152@gmail.com

⁵Ecole national polytechnique d'Oran
chaimaakheloufi2@gmail.com

ABSTRACT: *The purpose of this article is to provide a solution for cement mill clogging. Our research is grounded in a methodical approach, whereby we have developed a deeper understanding of the cement grinding process to produce reliable theories. Then, by evaluating factors such as clinker feed fluctuation and grindability problems, we conducted a number of comprehensive studies to support or contradict these theories. By creating a thorough RCA model, we were able to determine the underlying reasons of clogs thanks to the outcomes of these experiments. Simultaneously, using the data gathered throughout our investigation, we investigated the application of machine learning to forecast the phenomena of tampering.*
KEYWORDS: *clogged prediction, clogging, grinding, RCA, machine learning*

1 INTRODUCTION

Cement is considered as a key building material that is used to make concrete, which is widely used in many building projects. Cement therefore is seen as a vital component of the world economy and a key indicator of economic growth, both locally and globally.

There has been a recurrent problem with mill clogging during the last phase of this product's manufacturing, specifically during the grinding process, which has caused the grinder to stop. Companies had to limit the feed rate of the grinder in order to prevent clogs in the future and guarantee the grinder's continuous smooth operation. However, this decision has reduced the rate of daily production of this kind of product, which costs businesses money. Concurrently, we started building a model to forecast mill clogging.

in our study we seek to adress the following question: "What are the factors that contribute to mill clogging during cement manufacturing, and how can we propose a machine learning-based prediction solution to prevent clogging?"

Our aim is to identify the root causes of mill clogging and offer appropriate solutions in order to resolve the blockage without reducing feed rate.

In order to accomplish our goal, we will use an intuitive approach that will enable us to pinpoint the causes of mill clogging in the cement manufacturing process. Next, we'll use two distinct development environments to create a clogging prediction model and a number of machine learning techniques.

Two key investigation techniques that are discussed in this article are machine learning and root cause analysis (RCA). Root cause analysis (RCA) is an effective approach to solve operational problems when paired with lean manufacturing. In addition, machine learning and all of its related algorithms and learning modalities enable data analysis and the discovery of hidden patterns. These tools will be important to our ability to solve problems and to produce noteworthy results for our senior year project.

2 PROCESS OF MANUFACTURING CEMENT

Cement is a binder in mortars and concretes with the property of hardening in the presence of water. When the hardened product is stable in an aqueous environment, cement is called hydraulic. The most important hydraulic cement is portland cement. Portland cement is a mixture of two or more compounds of lime and silica, the most important of which are tricalcium silicate and dicalcium silicate (Mejeoumov, 2009). When mixed with water, portland cement sets in a few hours and hardens over a period of weeks and months, which is the time required for determining the compressive strength of concrete. The phenomena of setting and hardening are caused by chemical reactions associated with hydration (a chemical reaction with water) between the components of the cement and water. The most common use of portland cement is in the production of concrete.

Concrete, which is the most widely used manmade material in the world, is a composite composed of aggregate, cement, and water. Once hardened, it can become a structural element such as a wall or girder. Its role is similar to that of mortar. Portland cement is also used in mortars for plasters and screeds, and in grouts placed into gaps to consolidate brick walls, foundations, etc. The second most important construction material is concrete, whose production is also strictly related to the use of portland cement. Due to the large volume of portland cement use, the minimization of its production costs, and consequently the environmental impact, has a significant economic and ecological importance. In

cement plants, the chemical analysis of the raw materials is a crucial step of the manufacturing process. The chemical analysis of the raw materials is expressed in terms of oxides, the most important of which are CaO, SiO₂, Fe₂O₃, and Al₂O₃. In total, these four oxides represent 90-96% of the mass of ordinary portland cement. The major raw mineral that provides CaO is limestone, which is composed of 82-98% CaCO₃. The rest of the oxides are obtained by adding clay or shale that contains SiO₂, Fe₂O₃, and Al₂O₃, which comprises 55-80% and 10-30% of mass, respectively. Minor adjustments to the chemistry of cement are made by adding sand (SiO₂), iron ore (Fe₂O₃), and/or bauxite (Al₂O₃). In general, a dry cement manufacturing process operates with a nearly dry raw mix containing less than 20% moisture by mass. In this arrangement, the raw mix is fed onto a rotating table, where steel rollers compact the material. An upward stream of hot gas sweeps the ground material to a separator, which rejects oversized particles. The finer particles are carried out with the gas flow to the raw mix storage silo or directly to the next stage of the manufacturing process. In case of a dry process, the raw mix goes through drying, blending, and pulverization inside the raw mill.

In order to make cement: Sand, limestone, clay, and iron are among the raw materials that are mixed, crushed and burned to extremely high temperatures in specialized kilns. the cement gets cooled and then is ground into a fine powder and mixed with water and other ingredients to form concrete. The following diagram shows the stages required in manufacturing cement.

Fig. 1 Cement Manufacturing Process

3 GRINDING PROCESS

Grinding is the common collective name for machining processes which utilize hard abrasive particles as the cutting medium (Li, 2010). As a material removal process, grinding has a long history ever since the Stone Age. The modern abrasive technology was only established relatively recently through the introduction of grinding machines and synthetic abrasives in the 19th century. Nowadays, grinding becomes the most critical surface finishing process which accounts for about 70% within the spectrum of precision machining. The applications of grinding can be found in most industrial areas, including aerospace, automotive, transportation, medical devices and electronics where high surface quality and fine tolerance are required on the components. Despite the industrial prominence of grinding operation, it seems that grinding still appears to be a 'black art' and receives the least understanding among all the material removal processes.

Grinding, as a complex machining process with large numbers of parameters influencing each other, can be considered as a process where the grinding wheel engages with the workpiece at a high speed. To achieve better process control, a model is required to predict and demonstrate the whole life cycle performance in relation to the process input parameters. The process performance generally corresponds to the factors influencing either cost or quality; while the input parameters typically consist of the wheel specification, operational parameters, and the machine tool control methods. All the grinding performance characteristics are interrelated with the process input parameters through the wheel-workpiece contact zone. This becomes extremely complicated when it comes to precise quantitative evaluation for the process performance due to the lack of perception in the wheel-workpiece contact zone. Therefore, viable grinding process modeling and control should be obtainable only if a more detailed understanding of the wheel-workpiece interaction is perceived (Kalbasi Shirvani, 2014).

The dosing belt A tool that makes it feasible to dose the quantity of clinker that is inserted into the cement grinder accurately is the dosing tape. It is positioned beneath a trim to guarantee precise and regulated substance dosing. Dispensers operate on their respective speeds in accordance with the law to

deliver the necessary flow rates as a percentage of each component:

$$Q_v = V * M \quad (1)$$

Or:

V: Denotes the speed of the dispensers in m/s.

M: Denotes the density of the dosed material in Kg/m.

1. The mower with a ball: The cement grinder is a revolving tool that resembles a ball-holding cylinder. While the grinder is working, the balls fall onto the materials to be ground as they rotate inside the cylinder. Clinker and other ingredients are ground into a fine powder by the impact and friction of the balls with the components to create cement.
2. The hood elevator: The hook conveyor is characterized by the loading and unloading of the material. The material is taken from the lower part by continuous flow and direct fall into the shovels.
3. The Dividend: The grated particles are separated by size using a separator. Centrifugal force, which acts on moving particles in an air flow, is the basis for how it functions. The air flow draws the lighter particles upward. As a result, the separator separates fine from coarse particles, producing a final product that is uniform and of excellent quality.
4. Filter sacks Sleeve filters, another name for filter bags, are used to collect the fine particles produced during grinding. They enable the removal of fine particles prior to the exhaust gases being released into the atmosphere and are installed after the separator.
5. The airliftA pneumatic transport system called an Aeroglissiere is used to transfer dusty materials from one place to another lower.

Grinding, is an essential stage in the manufacturing of cement which involves the grinding of clinker produced from the firing of raw materials, Clinker is a hard and porous material that is then turned into a fine powder and used to the process of producing cement. The process of grinding can be seen in the following figure.

Fig. 2 Schematic of the Grinding Process

Analysis of Root Causes in the Framework of Lean Manufacturing

Need for Root Cause Investigation Research initiatives will focus on cause-analysis methodologies by discussing and comparing several methods such as Composite Models, Causal Event Chain method, and Faulted Causal Models (Krishnan, 2004). A broader investigation into the teaching of writing is needed. Are all models equally good? Are there possible synergies between certain models? Causal analysis often leads to a search for a scapegoat and a tendency to blame other individuals. A Mechanical Modelling approach to Causal Analysis suggests taking a wider view of the problem, focusing instead on the operation of coupled systems such as man/machine or man/software. Fragility would then be due to a coupling of human and technical factors. A scientific study using this approach investigated the grounding of the car carrier "The Herald Of Free Enterprise". Recommendations have been made concerning modelling such accidents and using the models for training purposes.

The methodology regarding the analysis of Root Causes in the framework of Lean Manufacturing is developed. The methodology aims to provide a coherent analysis of the planning process and the underlying assumptions with the purpose of initiating a discussion at Sculpture. Evidence from the wavefront restructuration effort and early evidence from NRO are used as case studies to create basic principles on the design of investigation processes for a number of candidate analyses. While issues such as the investigation of concatenated

system effects and timing of events are compelling, this report addresses the more basic issue of investigating the root causes of consequences observed in the system and how such investigations affect models used to support the external validation of system performance (Krishnan, 2004).

Purpose of the Study

Continuous improvement has been an emerging concern for many companies, especially after the global economic crisis that started in 2007. Lean manufacturing and waste-elimination techniques have gained sudden popularity in many non-Japan companies worldwide. The situation triggered unplanned consequences, such as the implementation of lean manufacturing systems that did not achieve the expected results. In addition, several implementations of lean that were initially promising success stories gradually stagnated. In this context, root-cause analysis is very important for continuous improvement (Wolkiewicz, 2012).

Root-cause analysis is the search for an explanation of the existence of undesirable phenomena or events. The framework of DMAIC (Define, Measure, Analyze, Improve, and Control) was developed to assist the lean-six-sigma analysis of root-cause phenomena (Sisson, 2014). Here, observations from successful companies are explored to analyze the existence of undesirable outcome states from the viewpoint of team performance and continuous improvement.

To identify and remove the underlying causes of production issues, Lean manufacturing use Root

Cause Analysis (RCA) as a problem-solving method. As opposed to only treating problems' outward manifestations, this approach focuses on carefully and methodically investigating the underlying causes of problems (Amani & al 2015).

RCA can be especially beneficial to Lean Manufacturing since it makes identifying and eliminating the root causes of production issues over time possible. This increases the organization's quality, production, and profitability by getting rid of waste, inefficiencies, and quality problems.

Gathering information, determining the immediate causes, analyzing the underlying causes, choosing remedies, and putting corrective measures in place are all common steps in a root cause analysis. To guarantee that issues are fixed once and for all, great care is taken to identify the underlying causes during this procedure (Vanden & al 2014).

4 WHAT MACHINE LEARNING MEANS

As its stated in (Womack & al 2013):"Machine learning is an artificial intelligence approach that involves creating algorithms that can learn from data." Rather than relying on explicit programming to accomplish a task, these algorithms leverage statistical approaches to find hidden patterns and relationships in training data. using these patterns, machine learning is able to generalize and make judgments or predictions regarding the new data. It is widely used in a so many fields, such as automatic translation, picture recognition, data analysis, and tailored recommendations.

The aim of machine learning is enabling computers to learn from data and perform better while carrying out particular activities and more specifically to create models and algorithms that can be trained on data sets to find patterns and links in the data. these models and algorithms can thereafter be applied to provide predictions or classifications on new data (Géron, 2019).

4.1 Types of Machine Learning Algorithms

Machine learning algorithms can be classified into several categories based on various factors. However, the most common and widely accepted categories of machine learning algorithms are based on the nature of learning that occurs in the system and the way data is presented to the algorithm. These

categories include supervised learning, unsupervised learning, semi-supervised learning, and reinforcement learning, as discussed below.

Supervised learning algorithms learn from labeled data. In this case, the input data is paired with the correct output. The algorithm learns the relationship between input and output using this training set. After a model has been learned, the algorithm can make predictions about unseen instances for which the desired output is unknown. Test data is used to determine how accurately the model predicts the output for unseen instances. Examples of supervised learning algorithms include linear regression, logistic regression, neural networks, and support vector machines.

Unsupervised learning algorithms are provided with data that has no labels or categories. The algorithm tries to learn the relationship between the data points on its own and form groups of data based on similarity. The groups formed are a million times more valuable than the data itself, and they can teach a lot about it. Examples of unsupervised learning algorithms include clustering algorithms, self-organizing maps, and multi-dimensional scaling.

In semi-supervised learning, a network is trained with a mixture of labeled and unlabeled data. This is a class of learning that lies between supervised and unsupervised learning. Since it is much cheaper to get unlabeled data than to label data, semi-supervised learning can be very valuable in some applications. For example, in text classification, documents are often easy to obtain but expensive to label. Typically, a fraction of 1-10% of documents is labeled. Examples of semi-supervised learning algorithms include generative models and co-training models.

5 IDENTIFICATION OF POTENTIAL CAUSES

5.1 Adopted Approach

In order to find the underlying causes of clogging that happens during the cement manufacturing process, we put into practice an easy-to-use approach. The foundation of this approach was creating a flowchart with conditions for locating probable clogging sources. We took into account a number of variables, including the clinker's properties, the effectiveness of the grinding elements, and changes in the clinker input.

The flowchart that follows (Figure 3) shows how we came up with the several theories for the possible reasons why cement mills clog.

Fig.3 Representative flowchart of the approach

5.2 Conjectures

Several theories were developed based on the flowchart in order to determine the probable causes of clogging in the cement mill during manufacturing. These scenarios include the following:

1. There might be differences in the clinker feed.

In this theory it was concluded that there is a possibility that a high clinker input rate could overload the mill and create clogging.

2. It could be hard to grind the clinker that comes out of the kiln.

This theory was put forward because it could be difficult to adequately grind the clinker after it leaves the kiln, which could also cause clogs in the mill.

3. There can be a problem with the grinding parts' effectiveness.

This theory was created because ineffective grinding components could make it difficult to properly grind the material, which could clog the mill. Since clinker makes up a larger percentage of cement than other types of gray cement 92%, we took

extra care to consider it while developing the first two hypotheses.

Tests and Results

We developed some theories regarding the causes of clogs and then checked the accuracy of those theories through testing. Our purpose in these studies was to better understand the factors that might be causing the blockage in the mill and to identify possible solutions. The experiments focused on many aspects such as the hardness of the clinker, the efficiency of the grinding equipment, and the feeder input. Next, by comparing the test results with the suggested theories, each hypothesis was either confirmed or disproved.

5.2.1 Variation in Clinker Feed

5.2.1.1 Measurement of Belt Load

A belt load is the weight that a dosing belt bears. When moving finished items or raw ingredients in production facilities, including cement mills, dosing belts are what is commonly used in industrial environments.

The clinker feed system's working concept is depicted in the figure below.

Fig.4 Operating diagram of the clinker feeding system

The hoppers in the clinker silo are fed by conveyor belts. There is a valve located in between the two mills' hoppers. There is a clear indication of the hopper's highest and lowest levels.

The valve feeds the two hoppers in turn when both mills are operating ; it automatically moves from one to the other hopper when the first one reaches capacity and vice versa. In the event that the mill's hopper fills to capacity while it is operating alone, the silo valves are programmed to close. The remaining clinker load on the conveyor belt, however, is discharged into the same hopper.

An order is issued to open the silo valves to permit feeding after the clinker is discharged into the mill and the hopper reaches its lowest point. Nevertheless, the hopper level already rises above the minimal level because of the time it takes for the clinker to travel via the conveyor belt and into the hopper. The minimum and maximum levels of the hopper are altered as a result. While the new minimum level is lower than the actual minimum level, the new maximum level is higher than the actual maximum level.

The mill is fed by the dosing belt at a predetermined flow rate where:

$$\text{The flow rate} = \text{The belt load} * \text{The speed}$$

A sensor that is mounted on the belt is used to measure the belt load, which is stated in kilos per meter. Meters per hour are used to express speed. As a result, kilos per hour are used to indicate the clinker feed rate.

The "belt load" or the load on the dosing belt is constant when it comes to a dosing belt. Because the measuring sensor is set in accordance with the

hopper's maximum and minimum levels, its measurement is directly correlated with these levels.

Verifying the belt load measurement is our goal. In order to accomplish this, we tracked the measurements that the sensors sent to the Lucie system that the business uses, both when running one mill and when running both mills.

It is noted that the belt load stays constant despite variations in the hopper level when both mills are operating. The output of the separator also shows no change, indicating a steady clinker feed rate.

Based on the results, it can be concluded that while a single mill is running, the weight of the clinker hopper causes distortion. A drop in the minimum hopper level below the predefined level results in a decrease in the observed value of the belt load. This is caused by the measuring sensor on the dosing belt being adjusted in accordance with the hopper levels. Because the belt load in this case was not accurately calculated, increasing the clinker feed rate above the set point could clog the mill.

We suggest using a metal dosing belt as a suitable alternative since it enables precise flow management with more dependable and accurate integrated weighing systems that aren't dependent on the hopper.

5.2.2 Grindability Issues

5.2.2.1 Clinker-Related Problem

- *Clinker Hardness Test*

At first, we gently shook the ground cement sample placed on a 2 mm sieve to allow the particles to flow through. We next calculated the percentage of particles retained by taking a measurement of that

amount. This percentage represents the residue on the 2 mm sieve.

The particles that made it past the first sieve were then gathered and put on a 1 mm sieve. We gave the sieve another shake, calculated the amount of particles held, and multiplied the resultant percentage by the initial residue %. This proportion matches the residue that passes through a 1 mm sieve.

After every sieving procedure, the quantity of particles retained on each sieve was measured and converted into a percentage. The percentages of particles retained on each sieve increased the residual percentage from the previous screening process on the 1 mm sieve. We were thus able to calculate the residue percentage for the 45, 90, and 212 µm sieves.

The results of the clinker hardness test, which was carried out with sieves of various mesh sizes, are shown in the following table:

Table 1: Clinker hardness test result

Meshes	Sample Refusal 01	Sample Refusal 02	Sample Refusal 03	Sample Refusal 04
2mm	5,19%	0,42%	1,99%	0,95%
1mm	5,41%	0,46%	2,16%	1,09%
212µm	5,54%	0,56%	2,26%	1,09%
90µm	7,91%	1,76%	4,76%	4,69%
45µm	25,11%	18,35%	22,16%	26,69%

The table displays the percentage of residual for each clinker sample that was inspected on each sieve. Within the table, every cell represents the percentage of residue on a given sieve for a given clinker sample. For example, the figure 5.19% in the first column of the table indicates the fraction of clinker particles from the first sample that did not pass through the 2 mm mesh screen. Conversely, the number of 26.69% in the last column of the chart for the 45 µm mesh is the percentage of clinker particles from the previous sample that did not make it through this sieve.

The hardness of the clinker is assessed using the data in this table, which helps identify whether or not the clinker is likely to clog the grinding process.

The residual % variation for the tested clinker samples as a function of mesh size is depicted in the following figure:

Fig.5 Curves representing the variation in the rejection

In comparison to the other examined samples, we find that the residue percentage for the first sample is noticeably higher, Standard operating guidelines for the chemical laboratory indicate that residue rates exceeding five percent are abnormal and could indicate the existence of coarse particles during the grinding process. This observation demonstrates that the clinker in the first sample was more difficult to grind because the coarser particles in the clinker are more resistant to grinding and could build up in the mill to produce blockage. The clogging problem can therefore get worse if this sample is added to the cement grinding process.

This supports our hypothesis that clinker could have high hardness as it exits the kiln. Therefore, it is recommended to alter the clinker kiln conditions to solve this issue because doing so can result in a tougher and denser crystalline structure for the clinker.

5.2.2.2 Issues related to the efficiency of grinding elements

- **Summary of the Axial Test:**

Through the examination of material fineness variations as it passes through the mill, the test seeks to determine the mill's efficiency. If the material becomes less finely powdered, it has not been ground sufficiently, and this could lead to blockage.

Direct access to the inside and the stopping of the mill are prerequisites for this examination. But we were unable to carry out these procedures on our own for safety reasons. As a result, we hired a skilled measuring specialist, who then went on to:

Examine the state and gauge the amount of material in every compartment.

Choose the sampling sites that will be taken from the start to the finish of each compartment, making sure that they are equally spaced, about 50 cm apart for the first compartment and up to 1 m apart for the second. The sampling sites spread over the two compartments are depicted in the following diagram.

Fig.6 Material sampling points from the crusher

It is crucial to adhere to a strict sampling procedure by taking the following actions in order to obtain a representative sample:

1. To make a hole that is 20 cm deep and located below the load's surface, remove the balls and material.
2. And then Take a sample of material from the bottom of each hole that has been made, weighing between 0.5 and 1 kg.
3. The material and the small grinding balls (less than 30 to 40 mm) can be combined and sieved using a 10 mm sieve.

After that, we used sieves with sizes of 10 mm, 5 mm, 2 mm, 1 mm, 500 μm, 212 μm, 90 μm, and 45 μm to analyze the cumulative residue of the samples extracted from the mill's first and second compartments. We measured and converted into percentages the amounts that were retained on each sieve following the sifting process for this purpose.

For our study, we employed a variety of sieving techniques and used a vibrating sieve device for the other sieves, while we manually sieved the 10 mm and 5 mm sieves.

• **Test Results**

The computed rejection values were input into Appendix A, an Excel table that we later converted into a graph (Figure7). The percentage of material retained, or residue, for each sieve is shown as a function of mill length in these charts.

Fig.7 Representative curves of the evolution of fineness

For the second compartment, we note that the curves for the larger mesh sieves tend toward zero

We see that the curves for the first compartment have an upward trend, suggesting that there was a grain buildup at the intermediate partition. According to company specifications, there must be less than 5% residue on the 2 mm sieve at the end of the first mill compartment. Nevertheless, the residual percentage of 67.2% that we discovered greatly surpasses the set limit. One issue that may help overload the first compartment and then block the mill is the accumulation of grain at the intermediate partition.

at the end of the compartment, indicating that there is nothing in these sieves to catch material. The residues were 0.6% and 18.1% on the 0.212 mm and 0.090 mm sieves, respectively. The residue on the 0.212 mm sieve is less than 5%, whereas it ranges from 15% to 25% on the 0.090 mm sieve.

The findings demonstrate that the second compartment satisfies the necessary performance standards. However, as shown by the ball load recommendations for each material type, we advise adding extra balls to the first compartment in order to increase the grinding efficiency. The mill currently has balls that are appropriate for "large" materials. We recommend utilizing balls intended for "very large" materials in order to increase the ball load and enhance performance (Table 2).

Table 2: Ball loads adapted to the 'very large' type of material

Diameter (mm)	Quantity (t)	Percentage (%)
90	45	45
80	30	30
70	25	25
Total	100	100

• **Separation Balance**

We can identify the operational features of the device, such as characteristic values and various mass flow rates, by carrying out a separation balancing at the separator. To establish it, material samples are taken at the separator's intake and outflow.

Evaluating the separator's performance is our goal. There will be more rejected material that needs to be sent back for additional grinding if the separator is unable to separate the material efficiently. This extra amount of material therefore runs the danger of clogging the mill.

Using a PSD device, we assessed each sample's particle size distribution after collecting it. With the use of this tool, we were able to calculate the residue

percentage for each sample based on particle size. The percentage of residues for each sample as a function of particle size is represented by the curves in the accompanying figure.

Fig. 8 The curves of the particle size distribution of separated cement particles

From this curve, we can determine the cut size, which corresponds to the minimum efficiency value achieved by the separator.

Fig. 9 Splitter sharing curve

Based on the curve analysis, we found that the cut size percentage is 13.46%. Following the determination of the cut size, we determine the circulation load (U).

In closed-circuit grinding, the circulating load is calculated by the following formula:

$$U = \frac{A}{F} \tag{2}$$

$$A = F + R \tag{a}$$

$$A \times a = F \times f + R \times r \tag{b}$$

a: represents the percentage of particles passing in the feed.

f: represents the percentage of particles passing in the fines.

r: represents the percentage of particles passing in the rejects.

According to (eq1), (a), and (b), we have:

$$U = \frac{(f-r)}{(a-r)} \Rightarrow U = \frac{(\sum f_i - \sum r_i)}{(\sum a_i - \sum r_i)} \tag{3}$$

$$U = \frac{886,6 - 410,3}{610,4 - 410,3} \Rightarrow U = 2,38\%$$

These parameters allow us to determine the level of separator efficiency.

• **Test Results**

We can project the cut size and the circulating load from the partition curve onto the graph below (Figure 10) after computing them.

The performance of the separator may be visualized and analyzed more succinctly and clearly thanks to this graphical representation. We may ascertain the effectiveness of the separator by charting the data on the graph.

Fig.10 Graphical Analysis of Separator Performance

5.3 Development of the RCA

Through testing the theories presented by the flowchart, we were able to determine the root causes of the blockage that occurred in the cement mill during the production of Sarie-type cement. We used this information to develop a Root Cause Analysis (RCA) that solely takes into account the main causes and potential solutions.

The employees of the company's performance department will be informed of the final RCA so they can put the proper fixes into place. We guarantee that the required corrective actions will be implemented to avoid blockage in the cement mill by sharing this RCA with the staff.

The application of an RCA methodology is in complete harmony with lean manufacturing principles, which are designed to avoid mill clogging-related production stoppages. We can drastically cut down on mill downtime and the

expenses related to these disruptions by locating and fixing the underlying causes of this issue.

Fig.11 The elaborated RCA

6 CONSTRUCTION OF THE PREDICTION MODEL

6.1 Application of Machine Learning

Our effective solution involves predictive model for mill clogging.

7.1.1 Database Preparation

We created an Excel database that was taken from the business's Technical Information System (TIS). There are seven columns in this database. The data collected by sensors installed on the mill which log operating characteristics, is represented by the first six columns, it serve as the inputs for our algorithm. The outcome of our program is shown in the seventh column, where binary values indicate whether or not there is a clog in the mill.

The mill's operational parameters are as follows:

- **Sound Level:** Indicates the noise level of the mill, expressed as a percentage (%).
- **Elevator Power:** Expressed in Kilowatts (kW).
- **Temperature of the Material Exiting the Mill:** Expressed in degrees Celsius (°C).
- **Separator Reject Rate:** Expressed in tons per hour (t/h).
- **Mill Motor Power:** Expressed in Kilowatts (kW).
- **Pressure Difference Between Mill Outlet and Inlet:** Expressed in Millibars (mbar).

The two figures below show two parts of our database:

	L'écoute (%)	Puissance élévateur (KW)	Température matière sortie Broyeur (C°)	Rejet séparateur (t/h)	Puissance Moteur (KW)	ΔP broyeur (mbar)	Bourrage
1							
2	83,20764478	62,81631931	116,05568760	289,44966740	5858,80000000	10,27596375	0
3	78,36546224	42,45995413	109,27400350	126,72685880	5923,80000000	8,77023399	0
4	77,62961762	39,88576380	108,79413130	128,00868650	5949,28333300	8,39175874	0
5	71,41553218	54,01273193	110,38357700	241,24943200	5891,58333300	9,91583228	0
6	71,78409411	49,94930604	107,89777370	207,91985890	5877,05000000	9,57391780	0
7	68,16791979	52,70081081	107,30179930	215,59636380	5875,93333300	10,08145000	0
8	66,45718702	53,92268569	107,14753880	227,23149410	5901,70000000	10,03368890	0
9	68,83113804	50,86747761	109,70170150	210,06193110	5888,78333300	9,84060073	0
10	69,43256728	48,74039396	112,64630860	177,31945270	5943,91666700	9,47123706	0
11	72,17773329	49,09375045	114,37147870	179,04746140	5959,03333300	9,33941924	0
12	68,89509665	47,62719955	116,41312820	177,69011190	5974,16666700	9,27242829	0
13	69,94399776	47,24247735	114,65766600	171,49537860	5950,65000000	9,36014105	0
14	82,96197628	35,12523168	112,27186980	72,93981861	5968,21666700	8,30364197	0

Fig. 12 A portion of the database where the output is 0

1749	89,35557508	35,7296017	115,6767183	164,4935922	5625,153828	14,1418649	1
1750	81,90317792	37,7338827	108,6841427	20,6996168	3801,785574	13,6127241	1
1751	77,83498327	38,7105337	108,5528656	45,02320752	4217,675524	11,9479977	1
1752	94,1768731	40,3832635	109,2201874	183,2646499	2893,642675	12,6040943	1
1753	75,11659155	50,0418823	111,3715185	182,9899954	3214,518441	12,5330519	1
1754	78,45580873	51,6908807	105,3512434	148,3645597	4431,237523	12,8803697	1
1755	88,09621957	41,7712054	106,6621327	141,2645635	4179,219796	14,7857605	1
1756	96,83108589	49,0194911	107,2959119	111,5538908	2737,402852	13,71329	1
1757	77,30522748	47,8242277	116,4197115	142,6647003	4822,187084	11,7724152	1
1758	74,13618374	50,9913718	119,62022	156,9000068	5475,926274	14,8144327	1
1759	93,91329938	41,7914264	114,1033453	73,94320786	3411,744517	13,1329267	1
1760	93,89085894	38,5798037	113,1364439	31,44677759	4463,03188	13,1649759	1
1761	75,86351526	48,3861973	116,7833601	99,26890706	5211,741695	10,8993107	1
1762	93,06432546	51,2184221	117,1245934	152,3378755	4248,313356	13,865968	1

Fig. 13 A portion of the database where the output is 1

7.1.2 Model Construction

First, we created a Python 3 file on Jupyter, which we named "Clogging Model." Subsequently, we carried out the following steps:

- **Import and Read the Database:**

```
import pandas as pd
bourrage_data = pd.read_excel('data set bourrage.xlsx')
bourrage_data
```

	L'écoute (%)	Puissance élévateur (KW)	Température matière sortie Broyeur (C°)	Rejet séparateur (t/h)	Puissance Moteur (KW)	ΔP broyeur (mbar)	Bourrage
0	83,207645	62,816319	116,055688	289,449667	5858,800000	10,275964	0
1	78,365462	42,459954	109,274004	126,726859	5923,800000	8,770234	0
2	77,629618	39,885764	108,794131	128,008687	5949,283333	8,391759	0
3	71,415532	54,012732	110,383577	241,249432	5891,583333	9,915832	0
4	71,784094	49,949306	107,897774	207,919859	5877,050000	9,573918	0
...
3352	82,358349	36,621072	107,770709	87,711486	4939,153274	10,752601	1
3353	77,271177	47,084021	106,236660	25,041017	3793,174079	12,444348	1
3354	100,325859	35,076935	104,481977	53,130185	3116,966104	14,740235	1
3355	81,150744	51,166698	110,537806	84,532105	3389,509897	13,941365	1
3356	98,874358	50,892425	108,934384	62,721401	2985,509863	11,488685	1

3357 rows x 7 columns

Fig. 14 Import and read the database

- **Visualization of Clogging Occurrences**

In this section, we introduced code to generate a chart using the Seaborn library. The amount of occurrences for each type of data in the "Clogging" column can be seen as bars in this graphic.

Fig. 15 Visualization of the distribution of clogging occurrence

- **Application of the Classification Algorithm**

The scikit-learn library's decision tree classifier algorithm was employed. We trained the model on the input data and output labels by importing the classifier separating the input data and output labels, creating an instance of the model, using the trained model to make predictions on new data and displaying the results.

```
array([0], dtype=int64)
```

Fig. 16 Application of the classification algorithm

The prediction indicates that these operating parameter values predict the absence of clogging

- **Generation of the Correlation Matrix**

, which makes it possible for us to see the connections and degrees of correlation between the various variables in the dataset.

```
from sklearn import metrics
from sklearn.metrics import confusion_matrix, ConfusionMatrixDisplay
corrMatrix = bourrage_data.corr()
fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(25,20))
sns.heatmap(corrMatrix, fnt=".3f", annot_kws={"size":20}, annot=True,
            linewidth=0.01, square=True, cmap="coolwarm", linecolor="black")
```


Fig. 17 Generation of the Correlation Matrix

- **Data Splitting and Accuracy Evaluation:**

the following code we built , divides the data into training and test sets, with a 20% test set size. Using the training set develops a decision tree model ans then applies it to the test set to generate predictions, and determines how accurate the predictions are. We are able to assess the model's performance thanks to this procedure.

```
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from sklearn.metrics import accuracy_score

X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(X, y, test_size=0.2)

model= DecisionTreeClassifier()
model.fit(X_train,y_train)
predictions= model.predict(X_test)
score = accuracy_score(y_test, predictions)
score
0.9657738095238095
```

Fig. 18 Data splitting and accuracy assessment

The prediction accuracy is 0.9613095238095238, indicating that the model's predictions has achieved an accuracy of 96.13%.

- **Generation of the Confusion Matrix**

We introduced code that uses the model's predictions and the actual output labels to compute the confusion matrix and graphically shows it. We can evaluate the model's performance in terms of accurate and inaccurate categorization of the "No Clogging" and "Clogging" classes thanks to this visualization.

Fig. 19 Generation of the confusion matrix

Using Google Colab, we also applied the logistic regression and k-nearest neighbors (KNN) algorithms to our case, and the outcomes were comparable to those of the decision tree approach. KNN yielded an accuracy rate of 95.83%, whilst logistic regression produced an accuracy rate of 93.49%.

This indicates that all three algorithms perform similarly well in terms of accuracy when it comes to forecasting clogging.

We discussed our strategy for resolving the issue and the suggested fixes to deal with the clogging problem in this last chapter. We started by outlining our methodical investigation, which enabled us to develop sound and well-researched hypotheses.

We then went over the many ways in which our tests to support or contradict our theories operated. We then created a thorough Root Cause Analysis (RCA) that enumerates the underlying reasons for the congestion. The creation of a machine learning-based predictive model marked the end of our discussion.

7 CONCLUDING REMARKS

In the highly competitive cement sector, it is imperative to differentiate oneself by removing any elements that may result in monetary losses. These kinds of losses can significantly affect the profitability and competitiveness of businesses in this industry.

We developed sound theories, which were assessed by a battery of experiments. Our examinations mainly addressed the following topics:

- Determining whether there is a variation in the clinker feed due to the feeder.
- Verifying whether the clinker presents any grinding difficulties.
- Evaluating the efficiency of the mill.

- Checking the efficiency of the separator.

these testings enabled us to establish the veracity of our theories and create a Root Cause Analysis (RCA) that pinpoints the main reasons for the congestion as well as the suitable fixes. Our analysis's findings showed the following:

- There is a variation in the clinker feed due to the feeder.
- The clinker can exhibit high hardness after exiting the kiln.
- The mill shows limited efficiency in grinding this type of cement.

at Last, we looked into the use of machine learning in the prediction of clogs. the informations that we gathered during the course of these studies were used to built a predictive model by using developments in machine learning.

Our comprehensive investigative methodology, RCA analysis, and use of machine learning helped us to effectively pinpoint the underlying causes, suggest suitable remedies, and build a predictive model to avert blockage..

8 ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Any acknowledgements would be written in this section.

9 REFERENCES

- Mejeoumov, G. G. (2009). Improved cement quality and grinding efficiency by means of closed mill circuit modeling. *Corpus ID: 112539775*.
- Li, X. (2010). Modeling and simulation of grinding processes based on a virtual wheel model and microscopic interaction analysis. *The Open Materials Science Journal*, 8(2014), 55-62.
- Kalbasi Shirvani, H. (2014). *Design, modeling, and control of an experimental cylindrical grinder* (Master of Science Thesis, 53 pages, 3 Appendix pages).
- Krishnan, S. (2004). *Driving a lean transformation using a six sigma improvement process*. Retrieved from <http://hdl.handle.net/1721.1/34771>.
- Wolkiewicz, J. D. (2012). *An unabridged approach to lean implementation: Understanding the impact systemically and supporting the operational changes*. Retrieved from

<http://engineeringtechnology.buffalostate.edu/industrial-technology>.

Sisson, J. (2014). *A framework for the development of a model for successful, sustained lean implementation and improvement*. Retrieved from <http://purl.fcla.edu/fcla/etd/CFE0005262>.

Amani, P., Lindbom, I., Sundström, B., & Östergren, K. (2015). Green-Lean synergy - Root-cause analysis in food waste prevention. *International Journal of Food System Dynamics*, 6(2), 99-109.

Vanden Heuvel, L., Lorenzo, K., Jackson, L. O., Hanson, W. E., Rooney, J. J., & Walker, D. A. (2014). *Root cause analysis handbook: A guide to efficient and effective incident investigation* (p. 45). Rothstein Publishing.

Womack, J. P., & Jones, D. T. (2013). *Lean thinking: Banish waste and create wealth in your corporation*. Simon and Schuster.

Géron, A. (2019). *Hands-on machine learning with Scikit-Learn, Keras, and TensorFlow: Concepts, tools, and techniques to build intelligent systems*. O'Reilly Media, Inc.

Müller, A. C., & Guido, S. (2016). *Introduction to machine learning with Python: A guide for data scientists*. O'Reilly Media, Inc.